

Anti-Gastric Ulcer Activity of Red Cabbage Ethanol Extract (*Brassica Oleracea* Var. *Capitata* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Gastric ulcer is a disease characterized by damage to the gastric mucosal lining. Gastric ulcers can be caused by the use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, *Helicobacter pylori* bacterial infection, smoking, and stress. The use of drugs tends to have negative effects on the body and safer alternative drugs from natural ingredients are needed. Therefore, this study aims to determine the anti-gastric ulcer activity of red cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *Capitata* L.) ethanol extract on the stomach of mice induced by aspirin and determine the best dose that provides protection. This research method includes sample preparation, extraction by maceration. Furthermore, the flavonoid test uses a qualitative staining test method. While the anti-gastric ulcer test uses a laboratory experimental method with a Posttest Only Control Group Design designs. A total of 25 male mice were divided into 5 groups with 5 mice in each group including cabbage extract at a dose of 21 mg/Kg BW of mice, cabbage extract at a dose of 42 mg/Kg BW of mice, cabbage extract at a dose of 84 mg/Kg BW of mice, a comparison of cimetidine 0.52 mg/Kg BW of mice, and the control was only given distilled water. The results of the study showed that red cabbage extract contains flavonoid compounds and can reduce the average number and severity of gastric ulcers in mice with an optimum dose of 84 mg/kg BW.

KEYWORDS: gastric ulcer, flavonoids, natural ingredients, mice, red cabbage, *Brassica oleracea* var. *Capitata* L.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The stomach is an organ in the human digestive system that is shaped like a pouch and functions as a container and digester of food, drinks, and medicines. The stomach must be well maintained so that food digestion is not disturbed. Things that can damage the stomach are food, alcoholic drinks, smoking, stress, and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. These things can cause wounds in the mucous membrane, or what is often called an ulcer. Gastric ulcers are one of the diseases that cause death which ranks 10th. In Indonesia, every 100 thousand deaths there are 8.41 people caused by gastric ulcer disease or around 0.9% of deaths. In Indonesia, Peptic Ulcer Disease (PUD) is found in people between the ages of 20-50 years [1,2]. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) such as aspirin, are the most

widely used group of drugs as anti-inflammatory and pain medications. However, the side effects that can occur, namely ulcers and gastrointestinal bleeding, will be a problem that must be overcome in the use of this type of drug [3].

One of the stomach diseases that occurs due to digestive disorders that are often experienced by humans is gastric ulcers. This disease can occur in the esophageal mucosa, stomach or small intestine [4]. Flavonoids have shown very effective and promising preventive and therapeutic potential in peptic ulcers [5,6].

Garlic and cabbage extracts can reduce the length of gastric ulcers, total acidity, gastric fluid volume, bacterial count, and histopathological changes caused by aspirin. On the other hand, both plant water extracts increase the pH

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value of gastric fluid. The results of this study indicate that both extracts can be used to cure acute gastric ulcers. Both plant extracts can be additional nutrients that are useful for food ingredients [7].

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

A. Research Ethics Clearance

The treatment of test animals in this study has received ethical code approval from the KEPK Faculty of Pharmacy Universitas Mulawarman, Indonesia with protocol number 00472164722211320230310080.

B. Appliances

The appliances used in this research were a blender, rotary evaporator, stirring rod, aluminum foil, injection syringe, analytical balance, tweezers, pin and scalpel, glass tools (Erlenmeyer, dropper, beaker, and bottom flask round, measuring cup).

C. Materials

The materials used in this study were red cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L.), distilled water, ethanol 96%, aspirin as an ulcer inducer, cimetidine as a positive control and physiological solution NaCl 0.9% as a gastric lavage after surgery. While the test animals used were mice.

D. Animal Testing

Male mice weighing 20-25 grams in healthy condition. Determination of sample size is done using Federer's formula, namely:

$$(n-1) \times (t-1) > 15$$

Where: n = sample size of each group

t = number of groups

$$(n-1) \times (5-1) > 15$$

$$(n-1) \times 4 > 15$$

$$(n-1) > 3.75$$

$$n > 4.75$$

E. Research Methods

Sample preparation

The sample used in this study was red cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L.) obtained from traditional markets in Samarinda, Propinsi Kalimantan Timur, Indonesia. Sample preparation included wet sorting, washing, drying, dry sorting, and making simplicia powder.

Fig. 1: (a) Filtration

(b) Concentration and separation of the extract

Extraction

Red cabbage extraction was carried out by maceration. A total of 142 grams of dry red cabbage powder was put into a maceration vessel then 96% ethanol solvent was added until completely submerged. Maceration was carried out for 3 x 24 hours with occasional stirring. The filtrate obtained from the filtered results was then separated from the solvent at low temperature and pressure using a rotary evaporator until a thick extract was obtained [8,9].

Flavonoid Test

Several milligrams of red cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L.) ethanol extract were put into a test tube, and then added with 5 mL of ethanol, shaken until dissolved and heated for 5 minutes. After that, a few drops of HCl(p) and a little Mg powder were added. Positive extracts containing flavonoids are indicated by the formation of a dark red color [10,11,12, 13,14].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Extraction

A total of 142 grams of dried red cabbage powder was extracted by maceration with ethanol for 3x24 hours. The filtrate obtained was separated from the solvent using a rotary evaporator and a thick extract with a blackish purple color of 29.91 grams was obtained. The results of the flavonoid test on the extract carried out using the Wilstater method by adding a few drops of HCl (p) and Mg powder, to the red cabbage extract solution, produced a color change from yellow to red which indicated that the red cabbage extract positively contained flavonoids.

Fig. 2. Flavonoid Testing with the Wilstater Method

B. Anti-Gastric Ulcer Test

The anti-gastric ulcer test was conducted using 25 male mice divided into 5 groups, namely group I (extract dose 21 mg / KgBW of mice), group II (extract dose 42 mg / KgBW of mice), group III (extract dose 84 mg / KgBW of mice), group IV (comparison group with cimetidine 0.52 mg / KgBW of mice), and group V (negative control group given only aquadest). The test was conducted for 6 days, where on the first to sixth days the mice were given a suspension according to their group orally as much as 0.5 ml as an effort to provide initial defense of the animal's stomach, on the 5th and 6th days after being given the suspension, an induction interval of 1 hour was carried out using aspirin as an agent that damages the gastric mucosa of mice. After six hours, the neck was dislocated and the stomach of the mouse

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was taken for observation. The following are the results of macroscopic observations of the stomach ulcers of mice.

(a) (b) (c) (d) (e)
Fig.3: Macroscopic Mice Stomach. (a) Group I, (b) Group II, (c) Group III, (d) Group IV, and (e) Group V.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Anti-gastric ulcer test showed that red cabbage extract can provide protection to the stomach from aspirin exposure. Red cabbage extract has activity as an anti-gastric ulcer with the highest dose of activity being 84 mg/Kg BW of mice.

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